

Covid-19 effects on ARTERial Stiffness and vascular AgeiNg: CARTESIAN study rationale and protocol

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SUPPLEMENTAL DIGITAL CONTENT 1

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Supplemental Table S1. List of participating centres that have obtained Ethics Committee approval as of 10 November 2020

Centre	City	Country
Wels-Grieskirchen Hospital	Wels	Austria
Macquarie University	Sydney	Australia
InCor – Instituto do Coração	São Paulo	Brazil
Federal University of Goiás	Goiás	Brazil
State University of Maringá	Maringá	Brazil
Faculty of Medicine of São José do Rio Preto	São José do Rio Preto	Brazil
Hôpital du Sacré-Cœur de Montréal	Montréal, QC	Canada
University Hospital of Québec	Québec, QC	Canada
University of Split	Split	Croatia
Cyprus University of Technology	Limassol	Cyprus
University Hospital in Pilsen	Pilsen	Czech Republic
European Georges Pompidou Hospital	Paris	France
Rouen University Hospital	Rouen	France
Lille University Hospital	Lille	France
Nancy University Hospital	Nancy	France
National & Kapodistrian University of Athens	Athens	Greece
Laiko General Hospital of Athens	Athens	Greece
University of Brescia	Brescia	Italy
Terni University Hospital	Terni	Italy
Sacro Cuore-Don Calabria Hospital	Negrar	Italy
Sondrio Hospital	Sondrio	Italy
University of Catania	Catania	Italy
University of Turin	Turin	Italy
Niguarda Ca' Granda Hospital	Milan	Italy
University of Pisa	Pisa	Italy
Azienda Sanitaria Universitaria Trieste	Trieste	Italy
University of Guadalajara	Guadalajara	Mexico
University of Bergen	Bergen	Norway
University of Porto	Porto	Portugal
Dokuz Eylül University	Izmir	Turkey
Giresun University	Giresun	Turkey
University College London	London	United Kingdom
University of Texas at El Paso	El Paso, TX	United States